

THE BEHAVIOR AND THE SOCIAL COSTS OF A MONOPOLY

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Abstract: This article examines behavior and social costs associated with monopolies from a microeconomic perspective, emphasizing implications of monopolistic practices on societal welfare. The primary characteristics of monopolies are defined, setting foundation for an exploration of relevant literature. The concept of social costs in monopoly contexts is explored, highlighting key contributions from economists.

Key words: Monopoly, Social Costs, Welfare Loss, Price Maker, Rent-Monopoly Power, Microeconomics

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola monopoliyalarning ijtimoiy farovonlikka ta'sirini kuchaytiradigan monopolistik amaliyotlarning oqibatlariga e'tibor qaratgan holda mikroiqtisodiy nuqtai nazardan monopoliyalarning xulq-atvori va ijtimoiy xarajatlarini o'rganadi. Monopoliyalarning asosiy xususiyatlari tasvirlangan bo'lib, bu tegishli adabiyotni o'rganish uchun asos yaratadi. Monopoliyalardagi ijtimoiy xarajatlar tushunchasi, iqtisodchilarning muhim hissalarini e'tiborga olinib o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Monopoliya, Ijtimoiy Xarajatlar, Farovonlik Yo'qotish, Narx Belgilovchi, Ijarachilik, Monopoliya Kuchlari, Mikroiqtisodiyot

Аннотация: Эта статья изучает поведение и социальные издержки, связанные с монополиями, с микроэкономической точки зрения, подчеркивая влияние монополистических практик на общественное благосостояние. Определяются основные характеристики монополий, что создает основу для изучения соответствующей литературы. Рассматривается концепция социальных издержек в контексте монополий, выделяя ключевые вклады экономистов.

Ключевые слова: Монополия, Социальные издержки, Потеря благосостояния, Установитель цены, Рента, Монопольная власть, Микроэкономика

Introduction.

The main purpose of this microeconomic article is to deeply investigate solid literature reviews on the topic of the behavior and the social costs of a monopoly. Firstly, we think that it is important to define the main characteristics of a monopoly shortly before finding literature reviews. Varian (2010) states that a monopolistic firm is considered as the dominant supplier for a particular

good or service. Mankiw (2008) clearly explains the behavior of a monopoly: Monopoly can change the market price and its output is regarded as the output of the industry; thus determining its supply with accordance to the market demand, all these exceptional features are sufficient enough for a monopolistic company to become a price maker in the market. Barriers, license and patents create stumbling blocks for other arising companies by decreasing their chances to enter the market and therefore making a monopolist even more powerful. Monopoly can be protected by government, trusted by consumers or the large scale of production is the main reason why monopolies can stand for a long period.

Initial points for the Social Costs of a Monopoly.

Many economists and scholars added their contribution to the development of studying monopoly behavior and its costs to the society. The true social cost of monopoly has always been an interesting topic amongst scholars in different periods. As above mentioned character of a monopoly: the monopoly is a price setter not a price taker (Competitive market). The firm that based on monopoly tries to get maximum profit by equaling its marginal cost and marginal revenue ($MR=MC$). If the monopoly restricts output and increases the prices, it will lead to the social inefficiency, this situation is named as deadweight (welfare) loss in economics (McConnel and Brue, 2009) (Figure 1 and 2).

Harberger (1954) has achieved to introduce methodologically the social costs of a monopoly and he created a new economic term called “welfare loss”, “deadweight loss” and Harberger’s triangle.

Figure 3. Harberger’s Triangle

Source: Modified from Wenders (1987, 458).

Harberger (1954) claims that while competitive market price is less than monopoly price, it can be a loss to society and consumers have to purchase its goods with $Q_c - Q_m$. Therefore, the triangle (ABC) which is indicated in the Figure 3 consists of the social cost of monopoly. P_mABP_c area shows the profit of the monopoly from its buyers. The following statements are his main assumptions:

“In the long run, resources can be allocated among our manufacturing industries in such a way as to yield roughly constant returns.”

“All firms are operating on their long run cost curves, the cost curves are so defined as to yield each firm an equal return on the invested capital, and markets are cleared.”

“The elasticity of demand for the industry’s product is unity.”

Harberger (1954) concludes that “all I want to say here is that monopoly does not seem to affect aggregate welfare very seriously through its effect on resource allocation (Harberger, 1954).”

After Harberger’s conclusion which is considered to be significantly impressive. Experts in this filed started becoming interested in both theoretical and empirical sides of Harberger’s study. Additionally, he gave a vivid explanation on monopoly and allocation of resources. Yet, Stigler (1956) states that we can see several drawbacks on the assumptions of Harberger, because the theory of elastic demand of unity seems to be more problematic. The reason is that monopolists never want to do an operation without a noticeable amount

of revenue. Because of this, if we rely on Harberger's research, the more demand elasticity is the less the level of welfare will be (Stigler, 1956).

An essential theoretical contribution as a good example to the field has been made by Tullock's (1967) study after the Harberger's. It is stated by Tullock that monopoly causes much extended social costs than the triangle suggested by Harberger. The consideration of the rectangle to the left of the triangle suggested by Harberger, PmABCPC in figure 3, is its concise contribution as per social cost additionally to triangle. It then creates a door for argumentative questions such as should the endeavors of clients and possible monopolists be considered socially wasteful. Thus, monopoly should incorporate its social cost.

Siegfried and Tiemann (1974) made a decision to learn empirically the social costs of monopoly by using the traditional way of Harberger (1954). Their method is strictly rely on a partial equilibrium framework, after their deep research, they finished the study with the following opinion: the result which is obviously shown in the analysis reveals that only few monopoly industries constitute a considerable welfare loss if the policy to decrease the monopoly power is introduced. Their recommended policy could enable to decrease the power of monopoly resulting a great benefit/cost ratio by restructuring the manufacturing sector.

Posner (1975) is a good study example which contributed towards the literature in which Tullock's (1967) study was approved about the social cost measurements of monopoly concluding welfare loss is not only Harberger's triangle but also the rectangular are on the left side of welfare loss triangle as well. As an approval he claims that monopolies attract resources into efforts while these resource could have efficiently been use in the competitive market, so opportunity costs of the resources are paramount social costs of monopoly. Posner (1975) divided monopolies into two distinct categories which are regulated monopolies and private monopolies, where he considered the former exceeds the latter category in social cost volume. When the author concluded he criticized all previous researches that had been done up to his time accusing them primarily on underestimating the true social costs of monopoly. In fact the costs of acquiring monopoly to society is much greater than was expected (Posner, 1975).

A few years later, the study literature of monopoly was enriched by Wenders (1987). In his study he approves Tullock's considerations about rent-seeking activities performed by consumers in the aim of defending consumer

surplus. At the same time, however, monopolists or potential monopolists would also perform such called rent seeking activities such as lobbying, giving bribery, hiring lawyers and so on in order to capture consumer surplus while consumers would perform parallel activities so as not to surrender to monopolists. Wenders concludes that under perfectly competitive market between the buyer and seller regulation leads to maximum welfare costs, which is equal to the cost under full monopoly price decision and rent seeking costs. In fact, Posner's monopoly total welfare cost is obtained if seller succeeds in attaining full monopoly pricing whereas welfare loss of Tullock's is greater when rent-defending activities are considered (Wenders, 1987).

One of the recent study in this sphere was done by Davis and Reilly (2000), they apply the ways of experiments and analytics to estimate rent defending and rent seeking behavior of monopoly. As a conclusion of different tests, they acknowledge that *"overbidding is persistent when bidders have different sharing rules."* It is also claimed that whenever rent-defending activities comes with its positive results, social costs of rent-seeking might continue to increase.

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